

Teamwork, Effectiveness and Efficiency Questionnaire

Focus - Questions

Communication - There was frequent communication within the team.

Communication - Team members communicated frequently in spontaneous meetings, WhatsApp conversations, etc.

Communication - Team members mainly communicated directly and personally with each other.

Communication - Team members often communicated indirectly or with the help of mediators.

Communication - Important project information was shared openly by all team members.

Communication - In certain situations, important information was kept away from some team members.

Communication - In our team, there were conflicts regarding the openness of the flow of information.

Communication - Team members were satisfied with the timeliness with which they received information from other team members.

Communication - Team members were satisfied with the accuracy of the information they received from other team members.

Communication - Team members were satisfied with the usefulness of the information received from other team members.

Coordination - The work done on the project tasks was carefully harmonized.

Coordination - There were clear and fully understood objectives for our team's tasks.

Coordination - The objectives of the tasks were accepted by all team members.

Coordination - There were conflicting interests in our team regarding the tasks/stories.

Balance in Individual Contribution - The team recognized the specific potentials (strengths and weaknesses) of each team member.

Balance in Individual Contribution - The team members contributed to the achievement of the team's objectives according to their specific potential.

Balance in Individual Contribution - The imbalance of members' contributions caused conflicts in our team.

Mutual Support - Team members helped and supported each other to the best of their ability.

Mutual Support - If conflicts arose, they were easily and quickly resolved.

Mutual Support - Discussions and controversies were conducted constructively.

Mutual Support - The suggestions and contributions of team members were respected.

Mutual Support - Team members' suggestions and contributions were discussed and developed.

Mutual Support - Our team was able to reach consensus on important issues.

Effort Our team put a lot of effort into the project.

Effort - All team members were fully committed to the project.

Effort - All team members made the project their top priority.

Effort - There were conflicts over how much effort the team members put into the project.

Cohesion - It was important for the team members to be part of the project.

Cohesion - The team didn't see anything special in the project.

Cohesion - The team members were strongly connected to the project.

Cohesion - The project was important to our team.

Cohesion - All members were fully integrated into our team.

Cohesion - There were many personal conflicts in our team.

Cohesion - Our team was united.

Cohesion - Team members felt proud to be part of the team.

Cohesion - All team members felt responsible for keeping the team together.

Effectiveness - According to the results, our sprint can be considered successful.

Effectiveness - All the demands of the sprint's customers were met.

Effectiveness - From the customers' point of view, all the USs of the sprint were achieved.

Effectiveness - The result of the project was of high quality.

Effectiveness - The client was satisfied with the quality of the sprint result.

Effectiveness - The team was satisfied with the outcome of the sprint.

Effectiveness - The product required little rework during the sprint.

Effectiveness - The product proved to be stable in operation in this sprint (App Store).

Effectiveness - The product proved to be robust in its operation in this sprint (App Store).

Efficiency - From the customer's point of view, it is possible to be satisfied with the progress of the project up to this sprint.

Efficiency - In general, the sprint was carried out in a time-efficient manner.

Efficiency - The project is on schedule.